

Big Promo

A stainless steel medical gurney with a green mattress and blue oxygen tubing. The gurney is on wheels and has a blue oxygen tube coiled on the side. The background is a solid grey color.

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PENAWARAN TERBATAS

▶▶ Klik Disini!